

Human Likeness and the Formation of Empirical Concepts

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The general problem with which I shall deal is how we recognize objects of experience, and, in particular, the formation of the concept through which we know what we think a given object is. Toward a solution of this problem, I shall suggest that one element in the formation of concepts of objects of experience is the likeness of the experiencer to himself. The way I think of this likeness must emerge in the account of its function.

I shall add to this suggestion that what we would ordinarily think of counting as concepts—those for which we can find words—demand an extension or distribution of this likeness among those who use language together. I have little confidence in a method that would look to words for the original derivation of concepts. It seems clear that sounds or written signs that are to pass for words must be recognized as words. No signal or indication that this is what they are will gain for them this recognition, unless the signal is itself recognized. A concept, as I am thinking of it, is presupposed in any act of recognition. It is, to speak broadly, the knowing what to think of an object that may be given.

The process of forming concepts has some life to it. My understanding of it is not complete enough that I dare take it too much apart into its elements. Classic classroom propositions like “this is a table” have always disturbed me when they were offered as prime expressions of knowing. They are very nearly empirical tautologies, if such a thing is possible. They are statements which simply would not get made in practice, except in the teaching of language or epistemology. It is possible, of course, to suppose that a child might be idly scratching with a fork beside his plate, and his mother might say to him, “That’s a table, you know.” But the child whose

response to this utterance was a mere assent to the truth of the expressed proposition would prove himself either unbelievably dull or a master of the arts of domestic politics. A proposal should finally stand the test of close analysis, but it is sometimes better at the beginning to make an estimate of the subject matter in terms of plausible generalization. Before making an exploratory operation it is well to have a general idea of where to start cutting. I shall begin, then, with what belongs to one popular image of the philosopher, an attitude of homely observation.

I shall take for illustration the experience of teaching professionally and distinguish with respect to it three senses of knowing. That sense of knowing for which I am seeking an account is that in which concepts play their most obvious role. It is represented in a man of whom we say, "He knows teaching," meaning that he is a competent judge of what takes place in a teaching situation. If we add in support of our statement that the man is an experienced teacher, we clearly are not saying that he has been experienced by a number of students. We do not mean, either, simply that he has suffered many, many hours of listening to himself hold forth. We mean that he has experience, and has significantly more experience in teaching than is usual.

Now this use in ordinary speaking of the term *more* with regard to experience must startle reflection. Everyone has experience, or is having experience, at least while he is conscious. It is possible that in degree of consciousness there is a meaningful basis for judgments of more and less with regard to having experience. But the limits of variation are too narrow to allow the proportion by which the experienced teacher has so much more experience than the inexperienced. It is quite possible, even, that in the classroom the consciousness of the moment of having experience is more heightened for the inexperienced teacher than for the experienced.

Having experience in the way of being for the moment affected is not the way one has it who is experienced. It comes closer to the sense of the proportion of the experienced to the inexperienced to bring in past time to give meaning. Length of time has, to all appearance, wider limits of variation with respect to quantity of experience than has degree of consciousness, or degree of being sensibly affected.

Nevertheless, it is not precisely our meaning to say that the man knows teaching because he has spent a lot of time doing it. The two are not necessarily connected. Teaching might by now have driven the man out of his mind. We do not say that he has had much experience, but that he has much experience. This way of having is distinctive, if the quantitative modifier *much* is to retain any meaning. One neither has a long series of past experiences all gathered up in a supreme moment of present consciousness, nor does one have such a series, in the sense required for “being experienced,” simply by the living through those times. The one who has all this experience is in many ways different from the one who was going through the experience he now has. Not the least of the differences is that the time for having a quantifiable experience is the present, even though a determination of particular quantity may be derived from length of past experience.

The way of having that is distinctive here is the way of grasping through concepts. The man who has a lot of experience and knows teaching is the man whose thinking is informed with rules for taking a wide variety of materials and situations that come up in teaching for what they are—for what they are, that is, in regard to the facts and purposes that make teaching what it is. He can tell pretty well whether he is getting something across or not, and he can judge whether it deserves the time it takes. There is a great deal, of course, that goes on in a classroom of which the teacher, simply as teacher, is not thoroughly competent to judge—things to

which he cannot give full and explicit recognition without diffusing his own function to the point of ineffectiveness. Some of these things are physical, some medical; some would be better understood by the psychologist or historian, some by the master of dramatic or poetic art; some, of course, are better understood by the students themselves. From the point of view of social justice, it may well be true that some of the members of the class have small right to their places there. This may be a fact of greater importance, finally, than that this teacher's classroom is a good place to learn. It is a fact, nevertheless, which a professional teacher, once the class hour begins, must all but ignore. He can give it explicit recognition no more effectively than does the mother who uses the example of starving children to try to get her own child to clean his plate.

This definition of a context of reference within which clearly discriminating judgments can be made is a prime characteristic of the fully formed grasp of a situation through concepts. The possibility of this definition, however, is not clearly explained through the concepts which presuppose it, nor through other theoretic concepts. The educator who knows education may know a good deal more about the elements and wider relations of teaching than does the teacher himself. With all this, he may quite well fail to understand teaching itself. In the classroom he may fail to give that definition to the situation by which he is able to discriminate, for example, between dullness, confusion, inattention or bias in the student and ineffectiveness of the presentation.

To find a source of explanation for this definition of a context within which judgment by concepts becomes possible, I shall turn to the two other senses of knowing which I want to distinguish. I have no suggestion that these ways of knowing are non-cognitive. That would be, at best, a very mixed use of words. I do not think that concepts play no role in these ways, nor that the drawing of distinctions produces absolute separations. I do think

that these senses of knowing are different, that concepts function differently with respect to the knowing, and that an examination of these other functions can illuminate the possibility of the detached, theoretic, or objective judgment.

Of a man teaching, or setting out to teach, we may say, "He knows what he is doing." We do not mean simply that he is capable of making the theoretic proposition, "I am doing or am about to do that which is called teaching." Neither do we mean precisely that he has a scientific understanding of how he is affecting his environment, narrow and wide. We mean primarily that he has taken responsibility for his action, that he is relatively sure of his determination to teach, even under conditions which he cannot entirely foresee.

This "knowing what he is doing" is not for the teacher immediately related to the possession of experience. The man who goes into the classroom to "get experience teaching," is still a graduate student who has not finally made up his mind. If he thinks he is becoming a teacher by getting experience, he doesn't really know what he is doing. Getting the kind of experience by which a teacher becomes experienced presupposes his having known all along, in some way, what he was doing. Otherwise, it is likely that he will turn out an experienced pedagogue, not a teacher.

In some ways the certainty of determination is most distinct at the outset of a demanding activity like teaching. The determination is not yet tested, but it is less likely to have become misdirected. In the midst of the experience and its unforeseen difficulties, the teacher may be taken up with what kind of a teacher he is. If this usurps the center of his concern, he gets lost. Under this kind of pressure he may say and even mean that he no longer knows what he is doing teaching. At such a time, a recollection of his earlier self or a reminder by another less touched by the facts of life of teaching may bring him back to himself.

There is a kind of innocence or hopefulness which characterizes the distinctly practical approach to experience of one who knows what he is doing. This is perhaps because the determination is so centered upon the accomplishment of a chosen object that the subject is simply expected to meet any instrumental conditions laid upon it. A determined man who counted in his determination the reflection that he might not prove to be so determined in the event, would simply not be very determined. This is the nature of practical determination. It centers upon making its object possible, not on measuring the potentialities of the subject. The object of undertaking to teach lies in the advancement of common understanding, not in the addition of one more teacher to society. To forget this is to lose the possibility of forming rules of judgment with any objective application within the limits of teaching. Attributes of personal charm or impressiveness lie somewhat outside these limits.

Nevertheless, no one becomes a true professional without finding out what it is like to teach. Mere determination will not give this kind of knowledge. There is a kind of blindness about rigid determination that prevents the merely practical man from being practical at all. He is unable to become the sort of agent who can bring about the object he sets himself. Knowledge of what one is doing teaching is prerequisite, but to know what it is like to teach is a way of knowing distinct from this.

A demanding occupation does something to the one who undertakes it. In this case, what it should do is make a teacher of him. This kind of experience is not, perhaps, so distinct in teaching as in many arts and skills which deal more directly with the natural environment. A situation like teaching, defined almost entirely in human terms, often does not draw its lines too sharply.

Someone who has spent countless hours practicing a musical instrument may one day find himself playing what actually sounds like the

music he intended. Now why should this be such a distinctive personal experience, when he is only doing at last what he has been trying long enough to do? It is because until he actually plays music, it is other people who are musicians. It is only when his determination to play, which makes the music possible, issues in actual music that he knows what it is like to be one who plays music. It is then that he begins to be a musician, something else than intending to play music.

This objectification, or better perhaps, realization of the subject of action, cannot be brought about directly through practical determination. The attempt misdirects and corrupts genuine productive intention. It results in "acting like," not in "knowing what it is like." Subjective realization is effected through a receptivity to the objective actuality upon which productive determination is directed.

Teaching works changes in the worker. Some of these changes, of course, can be quite disturbing, even dangerous. Teaching has many pitfalls. There is the sense of being bloated, which reflects the illusion that one's words are being multiplied by twenty-five eager minds. There is the fluency which one does well to watch closely. There is the casualness which comes from the many chances one will have to teach the same thing again, if one can forget that the student gets only one education. Put together a sort of largeness, a fluency and a certain superiority to history, and one can quite well affect the college teacher. One must sometimes wonder whether this is all one is doing.

Subjectivity alone, a sense of good intention, will not answer such a question. This is why it is necessary to have known at some time what one was doing teaching, to be able to recall this determination and to reapply it. But it is as dangerous as forgetting one's object to ignore what it is like to be doing one's work, badly or well as the case may be. It is necessary, finally, that the one who is doing one's teaching be a teacher. A teacher must be a

fully functioning person. In the case of one's own work the only candidate is, of course, oneself. This being a teacher, the one who actually does teaching, is not a practical object to work for, but it can be given back by the practically directed work. It is something which one does not produce but accepts or acknowledges in oneself. This receptivity to one's working is of first importance, for it is here that signs are given that original determination must be matured if its hope is not to become an illusion. The work which is making an ass of the worker is due for redirection.

What teaching makes of the one undergoing the experience may at a given time be a mess. He may be almost without hope though ready to acknowledge that he has had experience. Someone who knew him at the outset of his career may say that he is not the same person. Knowing what he is doing and finding out what it is like does not necessarily give him an integrated personality.

Say that knowing is an integral act, that it takes a person's full participation. Say that in knowing what he is doing and in knowing what it is like, a person is not necessarily the same. Then agree that the distinctive mark of the professional, the man who knows his work, is his responsibility—that he is the same person both in determining his work and in acknowledging it. What he does is like him. In this likeness to himself, then, we may have come upon a possibility of that detachment which is the remarkable subjective characteristic of objective judgment. For productive knowing and receptive knowing each take up the whole subject in an integral relation to the object, one active, the other passive. If it is the same person in either relation, the activity and passivity may balance each other off. The practical determination to effect an object adds to the object a supposition of contingency. I would not take the trouble to determine to teach if I thought I would teach anyway. For although I determine to teach without including in my object the fact that it will be me teaching, this is

nevertheless the fact. Teaching which is to be my teaching is contingent upon my doing it, even though the object is simply that something shall be taught. In having an object at all in a practical way, I add to it its dependence upon being my object, even though this reference to me is inappropriate to the object taken theoretically.

In being personally affected by my dealing with an object I withdraw contingency from the object. That which makes me a teacher cannot but be teaching, though to the physical elements it may be little more than a slight stir in the air. This withdrawal of contingency due to my being the one affected in a given way is in contrast to the theoretic requirement that an object of experience is what it is only with regard to the frame of reference in which it is taken.

Now it is interesting to note that the practical commitment to an object adds contingency to the knowledge that it is. The acknowledgment in oneself of the object withdraws contingency from the knowledge of what it is. This addition and withdrawal of contingency may be balanced off if essence and existence are differentiated in the object. It is only objectivity which presumes that the object is what it is.

To recognize that an object is what it is begins the theoretic way of knowing and distinguishes it from the two ways that experience brings to a likeness. To make this likeness—which is the justification for discounting the subject—appropriate to objectivity, it is necessary to undo the adding or withdrawing of contingency. This is what is done in the proposition of empirical fact. Just in so far as I determine to experience the object by paying attention to it, I take it as given, as non-contingent in that it is. On the other hand, just insofar as I am taken up with the object in what is for me a definite way, I take it as contingent in what it is upon the fact that it only appears to me, according to my way of experiencing it.

There are two grounds for the adjustment of contingency and non-contingency to obtain detached objectivity. The first ground is the likeness of the personal subject in his productive and receptive interaction with the object. Only this likeness, as a sign of balance, justifies taking the object objectively, as not containing in its experience subjective content. This likeness is not, however, a sufficient condition of objectivity, for it differentiates the object into two senses. One is its existence as terminus of a practical intent; the other is its character or essence as reflected by what it makes of one having it as object.

The other ground is the recognition that an object must be what it is. This is the primitive law of contradiction as the condition of the recognition of an object in general. The law of contradiction in this primitive sense, as informing the theoretic function of knowing in general, cannot perhaps be given appropriate formal expression within a logic of objective judgment. The concept in general is the rule that a given object be taken for what it is. The concept of an object given in the particular terms of experience must, however, be applicable in particular. The formation of such an empirical concept takes place upon the two general grounds just described. On the principle that an object is to be taken in its own sense, the empirical concept represents as cancelling each other the addition and withdrawal of contingency from its object. Now the productive and receptive interaction with the object, even though balanced, do not cancel each other with respect to the contingency of the object, for they retain distinct senses of this contingency ("thatness " and "whatness"). The addition and withdrawal of contingency by reason of the subject of experience should cancel out in the single sense of taking the object for what it is. This requires of the theoretic function of knowing something more than the general demand for non-contradiction. It requires that the cancellation be effected, not in the two

senses appropriate to productive and receptive knowing respectively, but in the one sense appropriate to the recognition of an object in objective terms. This cancellation of subjective reference is what is prescribed in the formation of an empirical concept. The contingency that is added to the object by reference to the experiencer's being intent upon it, is theoretically withdrawn in taking the object as given, as empirical datum. The contingency that is withdrawn from the object by reference to its being the object of the kind of subject who has such an object (what one who is a teacher must be doing is teaching; what one who is a table-seer must be seeing is a table)—this contingency, withdrawn from what the object must be, is theoretically replaced by taking the object as appearance or phenomenon. This balancing of denotative non-contingency with connotative contingency, within the single sense of detached recognition, forms the empirical concept of an object of experience.

Thus, the verbal formula, "This is a table," which does not express an empirical judgment apart from being seriously asserted by someone, does express an empirical concept. In this concept both the givenness, through the word *this*, and the definition, through the word *table*, are prescribed for a possible object in a balance, represented by the copula *is*.

An empirical concept is applied to its object in the proposition which experience may prove true or false. This proposition may use the same words, but it uses them to make an assertion under given conditions. The truth or falsity of the proposition is not determined by the balance theoretically prescribed in the empirical concept. It is determined by whether or not this balance is justified by a likeness in the subject intent upon and reflective of the object in interacting with it. Consequently, empirical truth or falsity is not wholly definable in terms of the detached way of knowing alone. On the other hand, if it is admitted that the productive and receptive ways of

knowing are distinct but genuine senses of cognition, the truth or falsity of empirical judgments need not be left an ineffable mystery.

Here is an illustration. An archeologist comes upon a flat, rectangular piece of wood about four feet by six, protruding from the dirt. In spite of the fact that he is intent upon this object and also knows that he is seeing it, he doesn't immediately make sense of it. He would not say, "That's an old piece of wood," because in his intentness the proposition misrepresents what he would mean by "that." He is looking for something more, even though all the object immediately makes him think of is an old piece of wood. He gets a look under one corner and notices, sunk in the wood, a hole that a table leg might have fitted. He is now put so strongly in mind of tables, which have legs, that he loses some of his intentness upon this particular object. He is not ready to say that a table is what this is. He digs around some more and, in fact, unearths the buried corner with leg attached. He has come to a balance in his two functions of looking for and being the finder of something in the object. For him the concept of this being a table now applies.

Abstractly, the denotative "this" can be made to correspond analytically with the connotation of "table." This can be done simply by thinking of "this" as signifying only what are to all intents and purposes taken to be tables. But this is the kind of proposition which no one would make for its own sake. In the situation of concrete perception, the possibility of recognizing an object is not given by thought alone. If there is recognition at all, it reflects something distinct from anything subjectively possible, something that is sorted out in interaction with an object and necessarily ascribed to the object.

Where does the reason lie that accounts for that poise which justifies detached observation? I doubt that we know, but empirical knowledge ascribes it to the object of the concept which understanding is able to form and apply. I have not really made out why this reason for poise cannot be

ascribed to the subject. This is a problem in the distinction and co-functioning of the mental faculties. I will only remark that ascription through a concept belongs to the theoretic function and falls under the condition of the primitive law of contradiction. It is the object which is what it is. A personal subject may very well be who he is not and not be who he is, and in the same sense, namely, his personal identity.

Some experience becomes objectively recognizable, some does not. The pain of another person, unless he is a saint, fixes the attention of the bystander to a great degree, but he is capable of acknowledging in himself little of what the pain is like (without affectation). The concept of another's pain reflects this in the fact that the pain is less given than it is definite in character. The empirical concept, then, of another's pain remains incompletely formed. A balanced attitude of detachment with regard to this area of experience is, in another sense, unbalanced. In extreme cases, it is psychopathic.

To return to the opening illustration, the teacher who is a professional has worked in an area of experience that gives some objectivity. The great experience which he has is great because of all the experience it takes to make a teacher. He has this experience, in contrast to merely having been through it, by virtue of his knowing all along that it was teaching which he meant to do. The one actually doing the teaching which he was determined should be done turned out, probably to his wonder, to be himself. Justified by his identity with his work, his being a professional and the categorization of a teaching situation come to the same point. With his experience, that is to say, with his personal identity, he is capable of making empirical judgments regarding objects within the categories of his teaching. As an administrator of teaching, of course, he may be anything but professional. It is interesting that pedagogy does not of itself refer to an area of experience that yields objectivity. The mere pedagogue is never quite professional.

Pedagogy falls within the categories of teaching, as teaching method. It cannot establish true categories of its own. As Socrates said, reality has joints.

I shall conclude with a rapid extension of the necessary condition for the formation of empirical concepts and the possibility of detached judgments—the condition of likeness in the personally active and detached subject.

The formation of concepts of objects of experience represents a kind of professionalism respecting sense experience as such. Directing attention to something and being occupied with it become so alike that it stands out in its concept with an indifference to the way it is taken subjectively. Through conception and granting a possible likeness among different subjects, communication becomes possible. For a sound intended as a word must be received as a word. If it is not foreign (in a wide sense) to the language of the listener, he hears it with the sense that he would himself intend a certain meaning by using it.

There is, in fact, a double likeness that appears with the use of language and underlies its reciprocity. The speaker speaks as one who could have his words addressed to him; the listener listens as one who might say the same thing.

A general theory of concepts should very likely provide a distinction between having words for a concept, whereby the concept is recognized in speech, and having the concept of an object, whereby the object is recognized in someone's experience. Knowing something and saying it come to the same point less often than may be supposed. That they should ever come to the same point, however, argues the remarkable condition of a common humanity—a non-theoretic, practical and responsive likeness among men which is all that could justify the professionalism of a science that categorizes a world of experience as public.

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